

Learning Difficulties Theories And Solutions

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Abstract:

The phenomenon of learning difficulties is one of the educational phenomena that have preoccupied educators, interested and specialists, especially since there is an international statistic indicating that the percentage of people with learning difficulties is 30%, and this percentage includes both male and female genders . Interest in the term learning disabilities was started by medical specialists with speech disorder, and after them came educators who revealed this phenomenon in the twentieth century, namely in the era of the Sixties . What distinguishes the phenomenon of learning disabilities is that it is not limited to a particular social group , the social or cultural background has no effect on its existence, but there are many other reasons, which may be biological, organic or environmental .

Also, learning difficulty can be associated with any person regardless of his chronological age, and average intelligence has nothing to do with learning difficulties , a child may have an average or above average intelligence level and yet suffer from learning difficulties in understanding the language, its applications and mathematical operations, or a disorder in social interaction and thinking, and these difficulties cannot be treated by traditional methods of education, especially Group Education .

Learning difficulties are perceived as hidden disabilities , the child may seem ordinary in terms of physical formation , but there are general manifestations that indicate the existence of such difficulties and are diagnosed only by specialists , and the symptoms of behavioral and academic learning difficulties , such as difficulty in social interaction and self-control of behavior , and thinking disorders , may overlap with disorders of understanding language and performing as competent and deaf .

One of the most important things that people with learning disabilities face is their inability to adapt and adapt to the educational tasks posed by regular education programs , as they are designed for all students without taking into account this category .the educational strategies المقدمة provided to people

with learning disabilities in the Arab world do not rise to the required level , while people with learning disabilities are often integrated with their ordinary peers without providing appropriate educational services for their abilities, which leads to their academic failure and dropping out of school. Attention should also be paid to highlighting the role of the family and society with its various institutions in diagnosing this phenomenon and finding possible solutions that help improve the educational situation of those students whose learning difficulties prevent their integration into their educational and social environment . In this research, a number of topics will be discussed that are closely related to the title of the conference and its first focus ” patterns and forms of learning difficulties and models explained ”, as for the research will include the causes of learning difficulties , their types and theories explained , in addition to some appropriate treatment strategies and plans , and the research will touch on the role of the teacher , who must distinguish between three educational terms with different connotations , namely learning difficulties , slow learning, and academic delays, and the research will also include innovative models in detecting dysgraphia

Keywords:

Introduction

The manifestations of learning difficulties are multiple and overlapping, whether developmental or academic, and each manifestation has its own method of diagnosis and treatment, the treatment of developmental difficulties is based on therapeutic programs specialized in training on concentration of attention , visual , auditory , tactile and spatial perception processes, and memory development, and academic learning difficulties including dyslexia, mathematical dyslexia and aphasia have their own therapeutic programs that seek to develop the ability to recognize and distinguish letters through audiovisual synergy, as well as the development of the ability to write through fine visual-motor synergy (eye-hand synergy) , As for the treatment of mathematical difficulties, its therapeutic programs are characterized by the development of the ability to distinguish numbers, understand household value and the logic of mathematical operations .

Given the multiplicity of manifestations of learning difficulties, their causes , methods of treatment and the breadth of topics addressed in theory , the research will deal with the theoretical aspects related to the subject literature in a concise manner so as not to happen boring repetition , especially in the first and second semesters, and the researcher thought that attention should be focused on practical aspects as in the third and fourth semesters, where they were included with a proposed questionnaire that helps the non-specialist grade teacher diagnose writing difficulty, as well as there is a proposed model for part of a treatment program in writing difficulty may help and open the horizon to teachers and interested and have a comprehensive vision in this framework.

In addition, special information will be provided about the forms and manifestations of dysgraphia , mechanisms in diagnosis , and strategies in appropriate therapeutic education, and this particular difficulty has been chosen and treated from multiple aspects due to its prevalence among learners widely, as the writing process is one of the complex mental processes that includes mental, cognitive, sensory and motor elements that may not be available to all learners ,

For example," in a study conducted in Egypt in 1988 on schoolchildren , it was found that the percentage of those suffering from dysgraphia reached 28.4%, which is a high percentage compared to the general percentage in the countries of the world" (elyasry , 2006), and another reason for choosing this difficulty is the ease of diagnosis among other difficulties by teachers , in addition to the experience of the researcher and her knowledge in this framework, which she acquired during her work in the educational field, and given the importance of the writing process for humans, as it represents one of the means of communication and is necessary for readers, dysgraphia it is necessary to pay attention and study because it is considered a cause of dyslexia , Therefore, the development of solutions for dysgraphia may contribute significantly to the treatment of dyslexia.

The last fourth chapter was devoted to the role of the teacher in the treatment of people with learning disabilities in general ,by adopting some principles that help him in this context .

Chapter One - learning difficulties from a pedagogical, psychological and organic perspective.

First: interpreting learning difficulties from an educational perspective :

Educationally, learning difficulties are referred to as the lack of development of mental abilities in a systematic way, which leads to an academic deficit represented by the inability to read, write or perform arithmetic operations and a general weakness in language and spelling, and this deficit is not due to impaired mental, auditory or visual ability, and the educational dimension considers that learning difficulties is an uneven pattern in mental ability, whoever suffers from learning difficulty may have normal performance in school subjects, but has a specific weakness in learning language or mathematics and is not caused by disability or environmental factors, such as mental retardation or emotional disorders , From an educational point of view , these difficulties are limited only to understanding , pronouncing and writing language , difficulty in perception and performing mathematical operations , the most prominent of these difficulties are aphasia , dyslexia , dysgraphia , mathematics difficulties, Dyscalculia, and Dysnomia naming difficulties .

Second: interpreting learning difficulties from a psychological perspective :

Psychological explanations of learning difficulties are concerned with the subject of attention as a case of developmental learning difficulties, attention is one of the psychological processes that affect the individual's ability to solve the problem, which represents a pattern of thinking. Attention is the ability to select the appropriate factors relevant to the subject from a set of auditory, visual or tactile stimuli, and in order to understand all the data and information related to a problem, it is necessary to pay attention to all the stimuli related to it. It is noted that people with learning disabilities have difficulty paying attention to and organizing important and appropriate stimuli, for example, someone with learning difficulties may pay attention to the picture in the book instead of focusing on the teacher's explanation, and he responds to external distractions that are not related to the educational task.

Specialists in cognitive psychology argue that difficulties are the result of a malfunction in the processes of cognitive representation,

Where the learner who has difficulty learning cannot pay attention to the appropriate stimuli, and this is due to a defect in perception, concept formation, remembering, problem solving and failure to develop thinking methods and knowledge organization, which leads to the failure to output perceptions in a verbal or motor form, and attention as a condition related to the psychological situation of the learner needs to input sensory data through the senses, such as sight, hearing and touch and then take them by logical analysis followed by verbal or motor behavior, and people with learning difficulties can not go through the stage of data input and processing logically, leading to a deficiency in thinking.

Third: interpreting learning difficulties from an organic perspective:

Many specialists believe that the causes of learning difficulties are due to environmental and genetic aspects, as scientific studies conducted on identical twins and first-degree relatives have proven that genetic factors, especially chromosomal abnormalities, are one of the causes of learning difficulties (Al-Khatib, et al. 2003, p. 312). Genetic causes are endogenous physiological that may affect the brain, while environmental causes are based on environmental and social factors and are exogenous such as improper nutrition.

Neuropsychology believes that the brain is the source of control and control in the human body because it sends messages through the transmitting nerves to all parts of the body, and the brain is the one that interprets the information and based on that the decision is made, and it is he who controls all body systems through the central nervous system," Strauss and Leitnin 1947 "believes that any damage to the brain, whether before, during or after birth may cause many disabilities such as cerebral palsy or mental retardation, and learning difficulties vary in their forms from one individual to another. Damage in the right part of the brain leads to a disorder in non-verbal behavior

such as understanding spatial relationships and sense of sound , and any defect in the left part leads to a defect in verbal behavior related to speech and language , analysis processes, logical infiltration, awareness of time and remembering verbal information, and damage to the cerebellum leads to impaired manual skills and errors in reading and pronunciation .

There are parts of the brain whose damage leads to the inability to recognize numbers and impairment in the formation of thoughts and imagination , and intelligent activities related to thinking and planning and cognitive processes that lead to multiple and complex learning difficulties .

In addition to the physiological (genetic) explanation of learning difficulties , there are other organic causes such as diseases that affect the mother during pregnancy and childbirth , such as rubella , malnutrition of the mother and the difference of the Rh factor in the parents , as well as lack of oxygen due to dystocia, or cases of poisoning, placental abruption and premature birth .learning difficulties may result from accidents to which the child is exposed, such as traffic accidents, falls that lead to concussion in the brain. lack and poor nutrition in the first years of the child's life leads to a lack of some chemical elements necessary for growth, which in turn leads to developmental or academic learning difficulties.

There are those who attribute learning difficulties to environmental factors, including radioactive environmental pollution, which destroys some brain cells, and from laboratory experimental scientific studies conducted on mice by exposing them to lead ,it was found that there was a change in brain waves ,which caused them to lose the ability to learn (Zeitoun, 2003, p .17). Also, there are chemical factors such as smoking and alcohol intake by expectant mothers that cause babies to be born weighing less than normal, which leads to a malfunction in their mental abilities .

Chapter II-manifestations of academic and developmental learning difficulties :

People with learning disabilities suffer from multiple and heterogeneous problems, which is difficult to classify accurately , as the difficulties overlap between disorders in thinking patterns and disorders in language and arithmetic operations , Johnson classified them in 1979 according to the negative interaction of learners with academic achievement and limited them to seven difficulties , namely disorders of memory , visual and cognitive spatial discrimination, disorders of verbal expression and visual-auditory fallout, motor perception, and attention . There are informal classifications of learning difficulties developed by teachers according to the frequency of their appearance by learners , and these classifications are far from the theories developed by specialists and relied only on the direct observation of teachers , considering that the behaviors of learners in this framework are real behaviors indicative of actual learning difficulties , including : common errors in spelling , letter recognition , auditory discrimination , difficulties in letters and disorders of auditory and visual

memory . Whether the classifications are nominal or otherwise, there are many symptoms and manifestations of difficulties that are difficult to detect.

The most widely accepted classifications were those of Kirk and calvent in 1984 (Salem , 2006 , P. 69) they included :

First: developmental learning difficulties .

Secondly: academic learning difficulties .

First: developmental learning difficulties include :

* Attention difficulty: these are disorders in the effectiveness of attention and linguistic thinking, which are primary difficulties (attention , perception , memory) , and secondary difficulties (thinking , and oral language), and attention difficulty results in side manifestations such as failure to finish tasks , lack of enjoyment , distraction, lack of continuity in activity, lack of concentration, excessive movement, lethargy, laziness, withdrawal and impulsivity .

* Difficulty of perception: it includes a disability in visual-motor coordination, visual, auditory and tactile discrimination and spatial relationships , and the difficulty of perception has secondary symptoms such as confusion between geometric shapes and writing numbers and letters in an inverted way , lack of distinction between shape and background (visual closure), lack of perception of the overall shape through parts, confusion between letter sounds resulting from impaired auditory memory , difficulty in knowing words and their semantics , lack of understanding instructions, inability to arrange parts of the image based on auditory memory .

* Memory difficulties: it is the inability to recall what has been seen, heard, practiced or practiced due to impaired visual or auditory memory, which leads to a problem in reading, writing and performing arithmetic operations .

* Thinking disorders : they are a series of problems in higher mental processes such as evaluation, comparison, reasoning, critical thinking, problem solving, decision making and calculations .

* Oral language disorders: difficulty in understanding language and the integration of its elements , and expressing thoughts verbally.

* Difficulty solving the problem : inability to solve the problem within its logical steps .

Second: academic learning difficulties :

It is a complex of disorders in learning to read, write, spell and perform arithmetic operations .

It is noted that academic difficulties cannot be separated from developmental difficulties , a learner who suffers from developmental difficulties will inevitably suffer from academic difficulties ,

dysfunction of the central nervous system is responsible for developmental difficulties that later cause academic difficulties . Academic difficulties can be limited to the following :

Dyslexia: dyslexia, which is represented by the difficulty of distinguishing, switching and deleting letters during reading, and the difficulty of understanding words and distinguishing sounds and using them during speech ,and storing information in memory.

* Dysgraphia, this dysgraphia is caused by an asymmetry between eye and hand movement due to impaired fine neuromuscular synergy .

* Mathematical dyscalculia: dyscalculia, which is an inability to understand abstract signs and concepts and the inability to explain mathematical operations logically , weakness in determining household value , understanding verbal problems , writing numbers in reverse , such as replacing the number 2 with the number 6 and the number 7 with the number 8, difficulty in coding and understanding mathematical language .

Aphasia, which is the inability to conjure up the appropriate vocabulary or its synonyms when talking , in other words, the inability to use expressive language .

* Difficulty in movement: Dyspraxia, which is motor difficulties caused by cognitive and visual-motor problems synergistically such as holding a pen .

* Naming difficulty: Dysnomia , which is the inability to remember names or give concepts and terms appropriate to the meaning .

Chapter III-educational strategies for people with learning difficulties / dysgraphia :

Manifestations of dysgraphia :

* Inability to learn to read what is written and not to write the letter according to its position in the word .

* Slowness in writing, writing without punctuation, lack of distinction between long and short tides, short movements, long movements and inconsistency of letters in the word (enlarging or reducing letters).

* Poor handwriting, irregularity in writing on the line and not leaving spaces between words (entanglement between them).

* Writing in different directions, such as writing English from the right and Arabic from the left .

* Writing all the letters in spiral lines, and mixing similar letters (v , w, b).

* Write letters upside down, such as writing the letter L in the image L, as well as mathematical numbers .

* Not to use margins, deletion, addition and replacement in the letters of one word .

* Talking to oneself while writing and feeling tired and exhausted .

Diagnosis of dysgraphia :

Formal diagnosis: carried out by specialists such as the diagnosis of the skill of visual-motor integration , the model of hand holding according to the evolutionary ladder , the examination of visual-auditory short-term memory , the examination of fine motor skills , the examination of visual perception and sequencing .

* Informal diagnosis: carried out by teachers inside the classrooms of students of basic grades, including :

1-copying and spelling :

* Copying selected letters of the Arabic language in their various forms by students according to a specific time standard , and monitoring the number of errors in the letters .

* Students copy a language text (movable spelling) according to a specific time standard , and monitor the number of errors.

* Students write a spelling text in absentia (test) according to a specific time standard , and monitor the number of spelling errors and errors in the writing method .

2-interview with parents to find out the family history in the context of dysgraphia.

3-direct observation of students in how to hold a pen and note all manifestations of dysgraphia and take notes to benefit from them .

Table No. (1)sample questionnaire proposed by the researcher to diagnose dysgraphia :

Student name: - - - - - grade: - - - - - school: ----- gender -----

Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Always		
				The pupil blurs the eraser while writing, which leads to tearing the paper.	1
				The pupil switches letters in one word .	2
				The pupil adds or decreases letters in the word .	3
				The pupil cannot read what he writes .	4
				The pupil is not obliged to write on the line .	5

				He writes Arabic letters from left to right and English from right to left.	6
				He writes words connected to each other within a 7. single sentence ..(That is, he cannot determine where 8. the letter and the word end).	
				9. The pupil writes the letter upside down as it appears in the mirror.	
				10. The pupil makes a change to the size of the letter (enlarge or reduce within one word).	
				11. The pupil does not organize his writing inside the page (from top to bottom) sequentially For lines.	

Note: the questionnaire is filled out for each student by the teacher through direct observation , and if the answer to the items of the questionnaire is with a degree of approval (always), the student suffers from learning difficulties, especially dysgraphia .

Educational strategies for the treatment of dysgraphia :

Most studies on learning difficulties indicate that dysgraphia is due to a weakness in visual-motor perception , and a weakness in neuromuscular synergy, so when developing any educational strategy for the treatment of dysgraphia, it should be adapted to the causative agent of this dysgraphia, and some of these strategies can be used that help students with dysgraphia study, and can also be used in dyslexia by replacing the writing process with reading, including :

- * Similarity strategy: in which students are trained to write similar vocabulary in some letters , and extract similar letters such as (mountain, sentences, work..).
- * Biological thinking strategy: helping students to remember and write letters by projecting life on the letter as if it were speaking in order to activate memory , example : I am the letter N is like a plate with an Apple on it .
- * Image Strategy: train students to write words by showing them an image, such as a bird image, for example, and then train them to write it letters or syllables .
- * Repetition strategy : in which the student extracts the repeated words in a text and practices writing them .
- * Modeling strategy: it is based on the student imitating the teacher directly for what he writes and reads .

- * Sensory stimuli strategy: it is based on the teacher holding the student's hand while writing and tracking directions .
- * Tracing strategy: it is based on the teacher's drawing of dotted letters , and the student follows them with a pen .
- * Copying strategy: where the student copies a certain text several times to recognize the shape of the letter .
- * Strategy of writing from memory : the pupil writes words from memory depending on previous stimuli.
- * Feedback strategy : the pupil writes the letters in front of him on a board with the teacher reinforcing him and giving him feedback about the mistakes .

There are other strategies that help develop muscles , such as aerobic exercises for the upper body, especially the neck and shoulders, including standing on the palm of the hand and knee and leaning on them with moving the body and trying to push the wall with hands, crouching and walking on the hands in order to strengthen the muscles and give them the ability to control the pen while writing .

In order to strengthen the fine neuromotor synergy , some activities can be employed with the pupils , such as using paste to pelletize balls , bead works , collage , filling empty bottles with cereals , using plastic kitchen utensils, fixing laundry tweezers on a rope and using tweezers to pick up objects from the ground, squeezing sponges filled with water, using dense colors to write letters with a finger .

To treat the difficulty of holding the pen, a wooden board made at a certain angle is used, which is placed under the pupil's hand while writing or a sponge pad is placed under it .

Chapter IV _ the role of the teacher in the treatment of learning difficulties :

The role of the teacher in dealing with learning difficulties and treating them inside the classrooms is an important and difficult role, whether the teacher is a specialist in special education or an ordinary teacher, this is due to several reasons, including that students with learning difficulties are integrated with the rest of their peers in the same classrooms and they are all taught and they need an individual teaching style, as the manifestations of learning difficulties are many and overlapping , and there are other hidden manifestations that the teacher cannot easily detect, and it is difficult for the teacher to follow one method of treatment because of the different degrees of difficulty , The role of the teacher in this framework can be limited to three consecutive steps, starting with the diagnosis, then determining the procedures of the treatment program, and finally, it is necessary to evaluate the target students in this treatment program to make sure how effective it is , and each teacher can determine the appropriate treatment program according to the data available in the classroom, as there is no :

- * The teacher should diagnose the learning difficulties of his students objectively based on the data and scientific evidence explaining the manifestations of learning difficulties .
- * The teacher should have a great understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of all his students with learning disabilities , and he should determine the nature of the difficulty for each student so that he can develop the appropriate individual treatment plan .
- * The teacher should realize that there is no one and only treatment program suitable for all students with learning disabilities , and he should always look for what is new and appropriate in this framework .
- * The teacher should take into account the integration of his therapeutic program based on the individualization of education , and the principle of fragmentation of educational tasks and their interconnection , while giving students sufficient time to complete their educational tasks within their modest abilities , taking into account the lack of frustration that may lead to their failure and the failure of the therapeutic program, and the teacher should take into account the principles of meaningful learning based on the accumulation of knowledge .
- * If there is a therapeutic program carried out by the special education teacher in the resource room, the role of the classroom teacher is to cooperate with the special education teacher in the completion of the therapeutic program .
- * The teacher should use sensory, visual, auditory and tactile stimuli during the program, but within the limits of the students ' mental abilities , in addition to using auxiliary and appropriate computer programs .
- * The teacher should review and evaluate the treatment program to ensure that its goals are achieved .

Note: the total skill is divided into partial skills starting from the character sequentially as in the following table :

Suggestions and recommendations :

- * Universities in the Arab world should commit to teaching special education courses in the faculties of Education
- * Developing programs to integrate people with learning disabilities with their peers in public schools in the Arab world .
- * Developing therapeutic programs in special resource rooms or replacing them with a supporting teacher inside the classrooms.
- * Encouraging researchers and those interested in universities and specialized institutions in the Arab world to conduct theoretical and Applied Research in the field of learning difficulties .

- * The introduction of a comprehensive educational staff system (subject teacher, counselor teacher, occupational therapist, physical therapist, support teacher, psychologist) in public schools in the Arab world.
- * Benefit from the experiences and expertise of developed countries in the field of diagnosis and treatment of learning disabilities .
- * The formation of special education departments in all ministries of education in the Arab world specialized in diagnosing cases of learning difficulties among school and kindergarten students and developing appropriate treatment programs .
- * Raising awareness of Arab communities on the subject of learning difficulties through the media so that these communities are part of the solution and not part of the problem .
- * Develop practical plans to guide people with learning disabilities across the professional disciplines appropriate to their abilities .
- * Integrating teacher education training programs with regular classroom teacher training programs, so that all teachers have the ability to deal with people with learning disabilities in the classroom.
- * To prepare curricula in the Arab world to adapt to the needs of people with learning difficulties , or to prepare special curricula for people with learning difficulties accompanying the curricula intended for ordinary students .
- * The curricula for basic grades 1-4 should be based on a child-centered learning methodology (learning behavior, values, basic language and mathematical skills) with the aim of mastering these skills by students, including those with learning difficulties .
- * The diagnosis of learning difficulties should be made by experts in this field , or teachers should be trained to distinguish learning difficulties from slow learning and academic delays .
- * Adopting the theory of multiple intelligences when developing curricula to solve the problem of learning difficulties .

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